

Comprehensive Analysis of Induction Motor Harmonics for Sensorless Speed Estimation in its Application to MCSA

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Abstract—In recent years, companies have been implementing smart sensors for autonomous asset monitoring. In this context, Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) is ideal to monitor induction motors due to its non-invasive and remote measurement capability. An autonomous MCSA algorithm requires precise, automatic and non-invasive knowledge of the motor speed to accurately locate the speed-dependent fault harmonics. Regarding this, harmonic-based Sensorless Speed Estimation (SSE) methods are the most compatible with MCSA, since they are based on the same principles. Among them, Mixed Eccentricity Harmonics (MEHs) are the most commonly used, due to their non-invasive implementation. However, recent studies have also shown the non-invasiveness of Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs) techniques. Therefore, the potential industrial use of both types of harmonics makes it necessary to determine which are more reliable for an autonomous MCSA algorithm. Hence, this paper aims to definitely answer this question by conducting an in-depth analysis of RSHs- and MEHs-based techniques attending to the most critical features of these methods: the detectability and accuracy of the harmonic used. For that, several related aspects are studied using three databases containing respectively: construction data of 3643 motors, 100 industrial measurements of 100 different motors, and 135 signals generated in a test-bench. The variety and extension of the databases allows for solid and general conclusions to be drawn that are applicable to industry.

Index Terms—Induction Motors, Fault Diagnosis, MCSA, Sensorless Speed Estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, many companies are adopting an Industry 4.0 philosophy, which is characterized by the use of smart sensors to determine the industry state and help make autonomous real-time decisions [1]. In this regard, induction motors (IMs) are a key asset to monitor, since they are the workhorses of industrial production, accounting for more than 70% of the energy consumed by electric motor-driven systems worldwide [2]. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to conduct a continuous diagnosis of their condition to reduce maintenance costs and avoid untimely outages.

Among the different diagnosis approaches, Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) stands out due to its non-invasiveness and remote measurement capability [3], the latter being critical in some applications (e.g. deep well pumping [4], [5]). This technique consists of measuring and processing the line current to assess the motor condition, principally by monitoring changes in the amplitude of certain harmonics

associated to different types of faults (e.g., eccentricity, broken bars, bearing wear and stator short-circuits) [6], [7], whose position in the spectrum depends on the speed.

However, for an MCSA algorithm to operate autonomously (without expert supervision), as required by Industry 4.0 philosophy, it is necessary to accurately locate the position of the fault harmonics in the spectrum. This is not a trivial process, even under steady-state conditions, as the presence of healthy harmonics can lead to misdiagnosis if the speed at which the motor is operating is not known with a high degree of accuracy [6], [8]. Furthermore, the speed must also be acquired automatically and non-invasively to meet Industry 4.0 philosophy. In this regard, physical sensors are expensive and often difficult to install. Thus, Sensorless Speed Estimation (SSE) techniques become the best option, since they can use cheaper sensors (voltage and current) and be easily installed in the motor power cabinet [9].

SSE harmonic-based techniques are the most compatible with MCSA [10], since both are based on the calculation of the line current spectrum to extract information from certain speed-dependent harmonics: amplitude/fault severity in the case of MCSA, and frequency/speed in the case of SSE. In addition, these techniques can meet the characteristics required by Industry 4.0 (accuracy, automation, and non-invasiveness), since they do not depend on time-varying parameters (unlike SSE model based methods [11], [12]) and do not need an additional supply source (unlike SSE signal injection methods [13], [14]).

In this regard, Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs) [9], [15]–[19] and Mixed Eccentricity Harmonics (MEH) [20]–[25] (also known as Rotational Frequency Sideband Harmonics), are the most commonly used in harmonic-based SSE techniques. MEH-based methods are currently used by commercial diagnostic devices (as MCEMAX [23] or EXP4000 [24]), since they are easy to implement: only the IM number of pole pairs must be provided (deductible from nameplate). On the contrary, RSH-based methods require the number of rotor bars of the IM (a parameter rarely known by motor owners, not usually provided by manufacturers), which so far has prevented these techniques from being implemented at industrial scale. Nevertheless, a recent work [19], tested in 100 industrial motors, shows that it is possible to use these methods in a precise, automatic and non-invasive way without knowing the number of rotor bars. Therefore, since both techniques might now be implemented on an industrial scale, the following question arises: Which of the two techniques is

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more suitable and reliable for an automatic MCSA diagnostic algorithm integrated in an Industry 4.0? In this regard, there is a clear lack of comparative studies that would allow to answer this question definitively. To the authors' knowledge, only [26] compares both families of methods, although in the context of non-invasive efficiency estimation and using only three motors. Moreover, [26] focuses solely on the accuracy of the speed estimation, leaving aside the detectability of the used harmonics, which, as shown in this paper, proves to be even more critical when deciding which harmonic to use (see Section VI for a detailed comparison).

Thus, the main contribution of this paper is to conduct an in-depth comparative analysis between the two main families of SSE harmonic-based techniques (RSHs and MEHs) to definitely answer the question above and therefore open the possibility to have reliable automatic MCSA diagnostic systems for the Industry 4.0. The main novelties can be summarized as follows:

- The work not only addresses the key aspect of the accuracy of the harmonic used but also its detectability, which is the second key aspect of any harmonic-based SSE, but which has not been studied so far in the available literature.
- Both key aspects are broken into sub-analysis features. Detectability is assessed through the analysis of the physical/design conditions that lead to the existence of a given harmonic and how likely they are to occur, the usual amplitude of the harmonic, its dominance in their operating bandwidth and the dependency of its amplitude with load, while the second key aspect through the speed estimation accuracy and whether this level of accuracy is sufficient or not to provide a reliable automatic diagnostic.
- Use has been made of three extensive databases containing respectively: information on the number of rotor slots and pole pairs of 3643 motors, 135 signals generated at different load levels and supply frequencies through a test-bench and industrial measurements of 100 different induction motors under different load and supply conditions. This is a noteworthy novelty compared to other works that use only one or a few motors, as it allows for solid and general conclusions to be drawn that are applicable to industry.

The paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the main characteristics and mechanism of generation of RSHs and MEHs. Section III introduces the methodology used to conduct the comparative analysis, as well as the characteristics of the databases. Sections IV and V present, respectively, the detectability and accuracy analyses. Finally, Section VII presents the main conclusions derived from this paper.

II. HARMONICS USED IN SSE

Before proceeding with the comparative study, it is important to describe the characteristics and mechanisms of generation of the harmonics used in SSE (RSHs and MEHs) from a Machine Theory point of view. This allows a better understanding of the conditions under which each type of

harmonics appear, thereby establishing the basis for the subsequent analyses.

A. Rotor Slot Harmonics

The discrete nature of the squirrel cage causes a periodic variation of the air-gap permeance (P), as well as the generation of magnetomotive force spatial harmonics by the rotor winding (F_h^{rot}). The action of F_h^{rot} on P produces air-gap flux components which induce in the stator winding a set of speed-dependent harmonics called the Rotor Slot Harmonics (RSHs). The frequencies of these harmonics are given by [27]:

$$f_{RSH} = \left[k \frac{R}{p} (1-s) \pm \nu \right] f_0 \quad (1)$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}$, being \mathbb{N} the set of natural numbers, p is the number of pole pairs, s the slip, ν the orders of the time harmonics present in the stator current $1, 3, 5 \dots$, f_0 the supply fundamental frequency and R the number of rotor slots/bars.

The existence of a certain RSH in the current depends on whether its associated harmonic spatial flux wave (SFW), created by the rotor, has a total number of pole pairs (μ) that the stator winding is also capable of producing, being $\mu = h \cdot p$, where h is the relative order of the harmonic SFW. In other words, for a given RSH to exist, the relative order of its associated rotor harmonic SFW (h_{rot}) must meet $h_{rot} \in h_{str}$. Regarding this, in a symmetrical Δ -connected machine, the stator can only produce harmonic SFWs of relative order $h_{str} = 2n \pm 1$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$), while the rotor can generate harmonic SFWs of order $h_{rot} = kR/p \pm h_{\nu, str}$, where $h_{\nu, str}$ is the relative order of the stator harmonic SFW through which the time harmonic νf_0 interacts with the rotor system. As h_{str} is odd, h_{rot} must be odd too for a given RSH to exist ($h_{rot} \in h_{str}$). Since $h_{\nu, str}$ is also odd, for h_{rot} to be odd, kR/p must be even. This is equivalent to state that an IM with a certain R/p only produces RSHs associated with a k that makes kR/p an even number. The latter still holds for Y-connected symmetrical machines or for line currents. However, in this case only components induced by harmonic SFWs whose relative orders are odd numbers non-multiple of three will appear [5]. Concluding, an IM only generates RSHs linked to a certain k if kR/p is an even number, therefore, not all symmetrical IMs are able to produce the RSHs of highest amplitude, that is, those associated to $k = 1$ (for example a four-poles IM with 30 bars). From now on, all RSHs linked to the same k will be called a family of RSHs of order k .

B. Mixed Eccentricity Harmonics

The misalignment between rotor and stator (eccentricity) gives rise to additional air-gap flux components due to the air-gap permeance modulation. When static and dynamic eccentricity coexist, these additional flux components induce the so-called Mixed Eccentricity Harmonics. The frequencies of these harmonics are given by [28]:

$$f_{MEH} = \left[1 \pm m \frac{(1-s)}{p} \right] f_0 \quad (2)$$

where $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

The existence of these harmonics in the stator current also depends on whether their associated harmonic SFWs have a total number of pole pairs that the stator winding is capable of producing. However, unlike the RSHs, the main MEHs, that is, those associated to $m = 1$, are always present, since they are produced by harmonic SFWs with p pole pairs ($h = 1$), as explained in [29]. Therefore, as long as some degree of mixed eccentricity exists, which is always the case due to construction tolerances [30], the main MEHs exist in any machine regardless of its design characteristics. Nevertheless, this does not assure that an inherent eccentricity is sufficient to distinguish these harmonics from the noise-floor. From now on, MEH resulting from taking the negative sign in (2) is called Lower Mixed Eccentricity Harmonic (LMEH), while that of taking the positive sign is called Upper Mixed Eccentricity Harmonic (UMEH).

III. DATA SOURCES AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Harmonic-based SSE techniques consist of obtaining the line current spectrum to locate and determine the frequency of one or more speed-dependent harmonics and then, using (1) or (2), estimate the slip. Therefore, there are three key aspects when selecting the type of harmonic to be used: detectability, accuracy of the estimation, and computational cost/implementation complexity. The first aspect refers to the ease with which an automatic algorithm can detect a given harmonic taking into account the physical conditions in which it appears, its usual amplitude, its dominance in the search band, and how its amplitude varies with the operating conditions. The second aspect refers to how accurate is the slip/speed estimation when using a given harmonic compared to a physical sensor or to another harmonic, as well as to how this degree of accuracy affects the diagnosis of an IM. Regarding the third aspect, both RSH- and MEH-based techniques rely on the same signal processing tools (FFT computation and peak detection within a search band), and their computational cost is determined by the minimum number of samples required, which is the product of capture time and sampling frequency.

A minimum capture time of 50 s is typically needed to achieve sufficient frequency resolution to distinguish fault harmonics from nearby healthy-state ones (e.g., broken bar harmonics from the fundamental component). As shown later in Section V-B, this 50 s capture provides sufficient accuracy with both types of harmonics to achieve a reliable diagnosis in most cases. Therefore, the minimum signal length requirement can be considered the same for both RSHs and MEHs. As for the sampling frequency, it is dictated by the highest-frequency fault harmonics that the MCSA system needs to detect. These are the mixed/dynamic eccentricity harmonics [28], whose frequencies coincide with those of the RSHs. Therefore, even when MEHs are used for speed estimation, the sampling frequency must be high enough to capture these fault harmonics, resulting in the same sampling requirements as when using RSHs. Consequently, both techniques lead to the same computational cost.

From an implementation perspective, an MCSA-based monitoring system only requires a current sensor and a DAQ with

Fig. 1. Characteristics of the database in [31].

at least 12-bit resolution to enable a low theoretical noise-floor (e.g., -128 dB in an FFT spectrum of a 500 kS signal), combined with either an on-site processing unit or a remote server. Given that the faults detected through MCSA evolve over weeks or months, while the capture and processing take less than a minute (for reference: approximately 1.4 s to process a 50 s, 10 kHz signal using MATLAB on a PC with an i7-8700 processor), such a system provides motor condition indicators in near real time relative to the fault evolution timescale. Since computational cost and implementation complexity are equivalent for both techniques, this aspect does not represent a differentiating factor and is not further analyzed in this paper.

In order to study the two differentiating aspects (detectability and accuracy) in the comparative analysis and make the conclusions as general as possible, two databases are used, as well as a test-bench to produce several signals, whose characteristics are described below.

A. Database 1: characteristics of 3643 IMs

This database is extracted from [31] and contains information on the nameplate, number of rotor slots and pole pairs of 3643 IMs. Rated power and pole pairs of the IMs in the database are shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen, the database comprises a wide range of IMs types, enabling its use to study the probability of finding motors in industry that are capable of producing a certain type of RSH family, a key aspect of the critical feature of harmonic detectability.

B. Database 2: 100 IMs industrial measurements

This database consists of 100 industrial measurements from 100 different IMs. The measures have been acquired in the context of consulting work for various companies, covering a wide range of real industrial applications, including submersible deep-well pumps (32%), surface pumps (29%), compressors (16%), fans and blowers (11%), and other applications such as extruders, agitators, pulpers, etc. (12%). It is worth noting that some of these applications are closely linked to specific pole-pair configurations (e.g., deep-well submersible pumps typically use $p = 1$ IMs [5]), further reinforcing the role of this design parameter in the analysis. Moreover, it includes 24 cases of frequency-converter fed motors, 21 cases of motors operating at slips lower than 1%, and several cases combining both conditions, which are the most challenging for a harmonic-based SSE [19]. In all cases, the motors operate under steady-state conditions during the capture time (50 s), which is the typical operating regime of most industrial IMs and the focus of this paper. However, it is

Fig. 2. Characteristics of the industrial measurements database.

worth noting that, given the diversity of industrial conditions covered by Database 2 (including 24 inverter-fed motors at different supply frequencies and various load conditions), the subsequent analyses inherently account for the small slip-frequency variations that may occur during the capture window in real industrial settings. Thus, this results in a very significant and varied data set that enables drawing solid conclusions about the feasibility of using RSHs or MEH in real industrial contexts. Regarding the acquisition, the signals have been acquired using a PicoScope 4824 oscilloscope (12-bit resolution, 80 MS/s maximum sampling rate) and a Pico TA167 current probe ($\pm 1\%$ reading accuracy $\pm 100 / \pm 500$ mA, DC to 20 kHz bandwidth), except for eleven motors that have been measured using a dedicated commercial device. In all cases, the input range of the DAQ was adjusted to best fit the signal level within the full-scale range, which is good practice in any FFT-based analysis to improve the noise-floor around the harmonics of interest. Since the measurements were acquired in the context of consulting work over several years, the sampling frequency varies across cases depending on the specific needs, ranging from 1.67 kHz to 200 kHz. However, in all cases, the sampling frequency is sufficiently high to capture the harmonic content of interest for the analysis (MEHs and RSHs). Signal lengths are set to 50 s, which provides sufficient frequency resolution to distinguish fault harmonics from nearby healthy-state ones. Rated power and pole pairs of the IMs in the database are shown in Fig. 2.

The spectra are calculated applying the FFT to the motor line current, expressed in dB with respect to the fundamental component. Finally, resulting spectra are used to study key aspects of harmonic detectability as the usual amplitude and search-band dominance of the RSHs and MEHs, as well as the effect that the differences in their speed/slip estimations have in the diagnosis of an IM, a key aspect of harmonic speed estimation accuracy in the context of MCSA.

C. 135 measurements from a test-bench

The test-bench (Fig. 3) consists of two identical IMs (2.2 kW, 28 rotor bars, four-poles): the one connected to a frequency-converter acts as a load, while the tested motor can be supplied either by the grid or a second frequency-converter. The speed is measured using a 1000-line incremental encoder, while the current is measured using a Pico TA189 probe (30 A range, $\pm 1\%$ reading ± 2 mA accuracy, DC to 100 kHz bandwidth). Both signals are acquired using a PicoScope 4262 oscilloscope (16-bit resolution, 10 MS/s maximum sampling rate) at a sampling frequency of 100 kHz, required to prop-

Fig. 3. Test-bench.

erly capture the encoder pulses, whose frequency reaches approximately 25 kHz at speeds close to 1500 rpm. With this setup, 15 signals are generated for three different fundamental frequencies (50 Hz line-fed, 20 Hz and 35 Hz) at three different slips (0.0067, 0.02 and 0.046), making a total of 135 signals. The current spectra of these signals are used to study the load-dependency of both harmonics and the SSE accuracy compared to the 1000-line encoder. In this case, the signal lengths are set to 150 s, since in this motor, MEHs caused by inherent asymmetry are below the noise-floor in many of the tested conditions when lengths of 50 s are used.

The resulting dataset is used to study the load dependency of both types of harmonics, an analysis that cannot be done with the industrial measurements due to operating restrictions. In addition, it is also used in conjunction with Database 2 to study the accuracy of both harmonics (RSHs and MEHs). In particular, the dataset is used to study and evaluate the accuracy of both harmonics (RSH and MEH) with respect to a high-resolution encoder under controlled laboratory conditions.

IV. DETECTABILITY

In this section detectability of both types of harmonics is studied, which depends on four key aspects: probability of existence, usual amplitude, dominance in their search frequency band and load-dependency.

A. Existence

As seen before, in a perfectly symmetrical machine, kR/p must be even for a given RSH family of order k to exist, a condition derived from Machine Theory [19], [28], based on the requirement that the rotor spatial flux wave must have a number of pole pairs that the stator winding is also capable of producing (see Section II-A). In addition, the higher the order k of the family, the lower the amplitude of its harmonics; for instance, in the spectrum shown in Fig. 4, RSHs of $k = 1$ (black circles), have higher amplitudes than those of $k = 2$ (red circles) and those higher than $k = 3$ (magenta). Therefore, it is important to analyze how likely it is to find motors capable of producing low order RSHs, as these have larger amplitudes, and therefore, are easier to detect.

For that, the 3643 IMs contained in the first database are analyzed to determine which is the RSHs family of lowest order k produced by each of these IMs. For example, the minimum value of k that makes kR/p even in a motor with $R = 28$ and $p = 2$ is $k_{min} = 1$, with $R = 27$ and $p = 2$ is $k_{min} = 4$, while with $R = 25$ and $p = 3$ is $k_{min} = 6$. Figure

Fig. 4. Spectrum of a two-poles 248 kW IM highlighting the RSHs of highest amplitude in each k family.

Fig. 5. Percentage of motors in which the lowest RSHs order (k_{min}) that can be produced is equal to 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 or 8.

5 shows the percentage of motors in which the lowest RSHs order (k_{min}) that can be produced is equal to 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 or 8 ($k_{min} = 5$ is not a possibility, since this database does not contain motors with $p > 4$). As can be seen, 70.6% of the motors analyzed are able to produce RSHs of $k = 1$, which are the ones of highest amplitude, and 81.3% of them are able to produce RSHs families whose lowest order is either 1 or 2.

Figure 6 shows previous information disaggregated by number of pole pairs: a red cross means that this value of k is not a possible k_{min} for the given p , no matter which value R might take. As shown, it is less likely to find $p = 3$ and $p = 4$ IMs capable of producing RSHs of low order. However, the most common type of motors in use have $p = 1$ and $p = 2$ [32]. In this database, 98.8% of $p = 1$ motors are able to produce RSHs of $k_{min} = 1$, while 89.2% of $p = 2$ motors are able to produce RSHs of $k_{min} = 1$ or 2. In addition, if only these two type of motors are considered (2748 out of 3643), it is found that 82.1% are able to produce RSHs of $k_{min} = 1$, and 93.3% are able to produce RSHs of $k_{min} = 1$ or 2.

As for the MEHs, existence of the main harmonics ($m = 1$ in (2)) only depends on whether the machine has mixed-eccentricity or not, and not on the design characteristics [29]. Since the occurrence of this phenomenon is practically unavoidable during assembly due to the accumulation of tolerances between the stator and bearing centers and the non-perfect rotor roundness, it can be assumed that all machines are susceptible to produce the main MEHs. This assumption is well supported by [30], where it is reported that manufacturers accept an air-gap eccentricity of up to 10%.

B. Amplitude

Previous section shows that the vast majority of IMs are capable of producing the main RSHs and that all of them

Fig. 6. Percentage of motors, disaggregated by number of pole pairs, in which the minimum RSHs order (k_{min}) that can be produced is equal to 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 or 8.

are susceptible of producing the main MEHs. Nevertheless, detectability of these harmonics depends on their amplitudes and surrounding noise-floor. Since the 100 industrial measurements have been acquired under real operating conditions, the noise-floor inherently reflects the electrical noise typical of industrial environments, including effects from power supply quality, electromagnetic interference, and, in 24 cases, harmonic content introduced by variable frequency drives. To study this aspect, the amplitudes of the most prominent MEH and RSH are determined, as well as their surrounding noise-floor, for the 100 industrial motors measured.

Figure 7 shows the amplitude and the surrounding noise-floor (NF) of the RSH (a) and Upper and Lower MEHs (b) of maximum amplitude, for the 100 industrial motors measured. Data is divided by vertical red lines in sets of same pole pairs in ascending order (1 to 5 from left to right); each solid horizontal line represents the mean amplitude of the RSH/MEH and surrounding noise-floor in each set of IMs. On the other hand, Fig. 8 shows the same results but sorted by ascending order of power rating. To better understand the analysis by power rating, Fig. 9 provides the percentage of motors with a certain number of pole pairs in each power rating range.

RSHs have an overall better Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR) than MEHs regardless of the power rating and number of pole pairs (SNR is defined as the difference between the harmonic amplitude and the surrounding noise-floor level). In this regard, the average SNR computed across the 100 industrial motors is 37.2 dB for the RSHs (-57.52 dB mean amplitude vs. -94.72 dB mean noise-floor) and 18.87 dB for the MEHs (-67.66 dB mean amplitude vs. -86.53 dB mean noise-floor). Moreover, RSHs have very similar mean amplitudes also regardless of the pole pairs and power rating, although a small decreasing trend is observed as the power rating and number of pole pairs increase. This can be explained by the fact that, in this database, as the power range under consideration is increased, there is a greater number of motors with $p > 2$. As shown in Fig. 6, the greater the number of poles, the higher the likelihood of finding motors where $k_{min} > 1$ and which therefore have RSHs of lower amplitude.

Fig. 7. Amplitude and surrounding noise-floor of the RSH (a) and MEH (b) of maximum amplitude (LMEH or UMEH). Sorted by ascending order of same pole pairs.

In the case of MEHs, they clearly present different amplitudes depending on the number of pole pairs: two-poles IMs have the lowest amplitudes (11 and 16.5 dB less on average than four- and six-poles IMs respectively). In this regard, there are 12 IMs where the MEHs are below the noise-floor (black bar completely overlapping the blue/gray one), being 9 of them two-poles machines, while RSHs are always above the noise-floor. It is also worth noticing that UMEH is usually the MEH of highest amplitude in two-poles IMs (the LMEH is only visible in 7.31% of these cases), while the LMEH is higher than UMEH in the rest of the cases. As for their relation with power rating, it can be observed that the MEHs have greater amplitude in the lowest and highest power ranges, and lower amplitudes in the intermediate ranges. This fact correlates very well with the dependence of amplitude on the number of pole pairs. In this database, the intermediate power ranges, (0.1, 0.2] MW and (0.2, 0.3] MW, are those with the highest percentage of motors with $p = 1$ (50 % and 52.38 %, respectively; see Fig. 9), which, as shown in Fig. 7, are the ones where the MEHs have the lowest amplitude. Finally, there is no power range where one MEH usually has a higher amplitude than the other.

The boxplots of the amplitude (a) and surrounding noise-floor (b) of these harmonics are plotted in Fig. 10. The first boxplot reveals that, in 75% of the cases, RSHs have an amplitude above -64.25 dB (Q1 mark), while in the case of MEHs it is only 25 % that are above -61.32 dB (Q3 mark), and that the RSH amplitude presents lower dispersion than that of the MEH. The latter is explained due to amplitude pole-pair dependency shown in Fig. 7, as well as the fact that MEHs amplitudes vary more with eccentricity level. Similarly, it is clearly observed how, in 50% of the cases, the noise-floor in the vicinity of the RSH is inferior to -97.75 dB (Q2 mark), while in the case of MEH it is only 25% of the cases which are below -95.22 dB (Q1 mark). This is attributed to the greater proximity of the MEH to the fundamental component, which causes spectral dispersion.

Fig. 8. Amplitude and surrounding noise-floor of the RSH (a) and MEH (b) of maximum amplitude (LMEH or UMEH). Sorted by ascending order of power rating.

Fig. 9. Percentage of motor with a given p at each power rating range (Database 2).

C. Dominance

Previous subsection shows that RSHs tend to have higher amplitude than MEHs and lower noise-floor in their vicinity, which eases their detection. However, this is not enough to conclude which type of harmonics are more detectable from the point of view of an automatic SSE algorithm. Most of them base the detection on extracting the frequency of the highest amplitude harmonic in a given search band. The most common approach in literature for this type of algorithms is to use a band that covers the whole possible operating bandwidth of the tracked harmonic (eg., [15], [18], [19], [22], [24], [25]), that is, a search band defined by evaluating (1) and (2) at $s = 0$ (no-load) and $s = s_N$ (full-load). Considering this, the industrial measurement database is used to study the dominance of the highest amplitude RSH and MEH inside the aforementioned search band. For this purpose, three levels of dominance are defined, which provide a systematic characterization of how likely an automatic algorithm is to correctly identify the target harmonic.

- Total-dominance: the highest harmonic in the search band is the MEH/RSH.
- Partial-dominance: the highest harmonic in the search band is not the MEH/RSH, but rather another harmonic placed just at the upper or lower limit, which could be avoided by narrowing the band a little.
- No-dominance: the highest harmonic in the search band is neither the MEH/RSH nor a harmonic placed at the upper or lower limit of the search band.

Fig. 10. Boxplots of the amplitude (a) and surrounding noise-floor (b) of the RSH and MEH of maximum amplitude.

Fig. 11. Percentage of motors according to the type of dominance: all cases (a), $p = 1$ motors (b), $p = 2$ motors (c) and $p = 3$ motors (d).

Figure 11(a) shows the percentage of motors according to the type of dominance: RSH presents total dominance in 76% of the motors, while MEH in only 55% of the cases. When total and partial dominance are considered together (black bars), the percentages increase to 98% and 83%, again in favor of the RSH. For a better understanding, results are disaggregated by pole pairs ($p = 4$ and $p = 5$ are not considered since the amount of motors is not representative).

Figure 11(b) shows the results for $p = 1$: MEH presents total dominance in only 5% of the motors compared to the 90% of RSH, while when considering total and partial dominance, the percentages increase to 73% and 100% respectively. This is due to the low amplitude of MEHs in $p = 1$ IMs and the existence of a harmonic multiple of the fundamental ($2f_0$) at the upper limit of the search band of the UMEH, which is usually the MEH with the highest amplitude in this type of motors (see Section IV-B). This problem is further aggravated in motors fed with variable frequency drives (VFD), as inverters tend to introduce even-order harmonics with higher amplitude (from Database 2 for $p = 1$ machines: -64.42 dB (grid) vs -51.15 dB (VFD)). In the case of RSH, the upper limit of its search band always coincides with an odd multiple of the fundamental [19], which can be derived from (1) using the condition that kR/p must be even for an RSH to exist (see Section II-A). Nevertheless, these odd multiples belong to frequencies much higher than $2f_0$, so they usually have a much smaller amplitude. This is because, according to Machine Theory, higher order harmonics tend to have lower amplitudes, as can be seen in Fig. 4 for the RSHs themselves with different

values of k , or as can be derived from Database 2 itself where the odd harmonics next to the RSH detected have an average amplitude of -73.67 dB, while lower-order harmonics such as $3f_0$, $5f_0$ and $7f_0$ have a much higher amplitude (-47.44 dB, -40.41 dB and -46.84 dB).

Figures 11(c) and 11(d) show the results for $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ IMs. In both scenarios, it is the MEH that presents the highest number of cases with total dominance, since in this type of IMs, the MEH tends to have a larger amplitude (see Section IV-B) and the limits of the search band do not coincide with a multiple of the fundamental which directly follows from (2) for $m = 1$ (main MEHs). Nevertheless, when considering both types of dominance, RSH still outperforms or at least equals MEH.

Finally, results are also disaggregated by different power rating groups in Fig. 12. As happened with the amplitude analysis in Section IV-B, the results of categorized analysis by power rating can be explained by the distribution of motors with a certain number of pole pairs in each range. In this regard, MEHs exhibit their lowest total dominance in the intermediate power rating ranges, which are in turn those with the highest concentration of motors with $p = 1$ in this database. Similarly, the only power range where MEH outperforms RSH in total dominance is the one that has the highest concentration of motors with $p \geq 2$ (40 % with $p \geq 3$) and, as mentioned before, MEH tends to have a larger amplitude in these motors and the limits of the search band do not coincide with a multiple of the fundamental.

It is important to note that total dominance problems of MEHs in $p = 1$ IMs due to the $2f_0$ component at the upper limit of the search band can be avoided by shortening the search window. However, this can lead to a substantial reduction in the detectable slip range, due to the narrow operating bandwidth of this harmonic. For example, using (2), it can be directly verified that if the MEH search band is shortened by only 0.5 Hz in a typical $p = 1$ 28 bars IM, no slip below 1% can be detected, which leaves low slip motors (as high-power ones), without slip estimation. On the other hand, using (1), it can be verified that if the same shortening is applied to the RSH search band, any slip above 0.036% could be detected, which only leaves out extreme no-load conditions (in which no industry motor runs permanently).

In this regard, dominance problems caused by the existence of higher amplitude harmonics in the search band other than those located at the upper limit are easier to deal with in the case of RSHs. While the number of main MEHs is at most two, the number of RSHs can be much larger (ν takes different values: Fig. 4). Therefore, it is possible that while a RSH associated with a given ν does not show total or partial dominance, another RSH associated with another ν does. This fact can be exploited by simultaneously searching for several RSHs, then estimating the speed through each of them, and finally discarding those erroneous estimates (when a harmonic that is not the RSH has been detected) by eliminating outliers [19].

Fig. 12. Percentage of motors according to the type of dominance for different power ranges: (0.0, 0.1] MW (a), (0.1, 0.2] MW (b), (0.2, 0.3] MW (c) and (0.3, 2.2] MW (d).

Fig. 13. RSHs average amplitudes for three different slips at three different supply frequencies: 50 Hz line-fed (a), 35 Hz (b) and 20 Hz (c).

D. Load-dependency

Finally, the variation in the amplitude of these harmonics with respect to the load level must be analyzed. Since peak efficiency typically falls between 75 and 100% [2] and there is always some degree of oversizing, most IMs in industry operate between 70% and 100% of their rated load. Therefore, harmonics whose amplitude is higher at higher loads will be easier to detect. To study this phenomenon, the battery of 135 lab currents described in Section III-C is used. In this regard, the amplitude of several RSHs ($k = 1, \nu = \pm 1, \pm 3$) and both MEHs are recorded for each of the 135 signals.

Figures 13 and 14 show, respectively, the RSHs and MEHs mean amplitudes for each of the operating conditions, averaging 15 signals per case. The results show that the maximum amplitudes of the RSHs(-3, -1, +3) occur at high loads, while in the case of RSH(-1) it occurs at low loads. As for the MEHs, it is observed that the maximum amplitude of both harmonics happens at low and very low loads. Concluding, RSHs are easier to detect at high load, where most IMs operate.

V. ACCURACY

In this section, the accuracies of the speed estimation provided by the MEH and RSH are compared with each other

Fig. 14. MEHs average amplitudes for three different slips at three different supply frequencies: 50 Hz line-fed (a), 35 Hz (b) and 20 Hz (c).

and with a 1000-line encoder (Subsection V-A), analyzing to the effect that the committed error has in the diagnosis of an IM (Subsection V-B).

A. Speed accuracy

The formulas to estimate the speed from the MEH and the RSH can be derived from (1) and (2) resulting in:

$$MEH \rightarrow n_h = \pm 60 \left(\frac{f_{MEH} - f_0}{m} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$RSH \rightarrow n_h = \frac{60f_0}{p} \left(1 - \frac{\left[k \frac{R}{p} \pm \nu \right] f_0 - f_{RSH}}{k \frac{R}{p} f_0} \right) \quad (4)$$

where n_h denotes the rotor speed (in rpm) estimated through the harmonic.

If the parameters of the formula are known (kR/p in (4) can be derived automatically and non-invasively using [19]), then, the only error comes from estimating f_0 , f_{MEH} and f_{RSH} . Differentiating (3) and (4) with respect to these three frequencies and then discretizing, the speed error is expressed as a function of the estimation errors of these three frequencies:

$$MEH \rightarrow \Delta n_h = \mp \frac{60}{m} \Delta f_0 \pm \frac{60}{m} \Delta f_{MEH} \quad (5)$$

$$RSH \rightarrow \Delta n_h = \mp \frac{60\nu}{kR} \Delta f_0 + \frac{60}{kR} \Delta f_{RSH}$$

Assuming a constant speed (which is common in many IMs), the maximum error in the frequency estimation of any harmonic is determined by the frequency resolution: $1/(2T_{cap})$ (T_{cap} is the capturing time). Assuming that the main harmonics are used ($k = 1, \nu = -1$ and $m = 1$), the MEH error is R times higher than that of the RSH (according to the database from [31], 75% of the motors have $R > 28$). Therefore, from a theoretical point of view, RSHs are more accurate for estimating speed than MEHs.

The battery of signals described in Section III-C is used to validate the previous theoretical conclusion. For each of these signals, f_0 , main f_{MEHs} ($m = 1$) and main f_{RSH} ($k = 1, \nu = -1$) are extracted. Next, the speed is obtained using (3)

Fig. 15. RSH and MEH absolute speed errors for three slips at three supply frequencies: 50 Hz line-fed (a), 35 Hz (b) and 20 Hz (c).

and (4). Finally, the absolute speed error with respect to the encoder ($e_{\text{speed}} = |n_h - n_e|$, where n_e is the encoder-measured speed) is calculated. In the case of MEHs, the lowest speed error between LMEH and UMEH is recorded for each signal.

Figure 15 depicts the RSH and MEH speed errors (average of 15 signals per case) for each supply frequency and slip (load condition). The speed error when using any of the harmonics is, overall, very low. However, RSHs are generally much more accurate than MEHs: up to 16.3 times more in the case of 20 Hz at 0.046 slip. MEHs only exhibit a superior accuracy when the motor is fed at 50 Hz with low and very low load. This is because the slip-frequency ($s f_0$) is much more unstable when the motor is fed from the grid and has little load. This instability causes fluctuations in the frequency of the speed-dependent harmonics. These fluctuations are more pronounced in those harmonics with a large bandwidth such as RSHs. In turn, these fluctuations cause the harmonic energy to be spread over more frequency bins. This increases the chances that the bin with the highest amplitude (the one detected by an SSE algorithm) is farther away from the one corresponding to the frequency associated with the average speed during the capture time (the one given by the 1000-line encoder).

To illustrate this phenomenon, Fig. 16a shows the spectrum of the test-bench motor when it is fed from the grid at 50 Hz and operated at 0.0067 slip. As can be seen, the harmonic energy has been spread over several frequency bins (the harmonic is not a clear thin peak). The consequence is that the bins corresponding to the average speed given by the encoder (yellow diamond) and the bin corresponding to the maximum amplitude (red diamond) are separated 0.0946 Hz resulting in a speed error of 0.202 rpm. However, when the motor is fed from the frequency converter at 50 Hz and same slip (Fig. 16b), the harmonic leakage is dramatically reduced (the harmonic is a clear thin peak), being now the frequency error 0.0015 Hz and the speed error only 0.0033 rpm (in both cases the relationship between the speed error and frequency error is governed by the coefficient of (5): $60/(kR) = 60/(1 \cdot 28) = 2.14$).

In summary, RSHs provide a much more accurate estimation than MEHs as per theoretical and experimental results. However, it is recommended to reach a compromise with the capture time: a signal long enough to have a good frequency

Fig. 16. Test-bench motor spectrum at two different conditions showing the consequences of slip-frequency instabilities: $s = 0.0067$, $f_0 = 50$ Hz grid (a) and $s = 0.0067$, $f_0 = 50$ Hz frequency converter (b).

resolution to detect fault harmonics, but short enough to reduce the speed error caused by a possible slip-frequency instability.

B. Diagnosis reliability

Last aspect to assess is how the error committed in the speed estimation affects the diagnosis reliability of an IM when automatically locating the fault harmonics through the estimated speed. To do this, the 100 industrial measurements database is used, selecting only the 23 IMs with total or partial dominance of both harmonics, and with visible Broken Bar Harmonics (BBHs: used to detect rotor electrical asymmetries; frequencies given by [19]: $(1 - 2s) f_0$ and $(q(1 - s) \pm s) f_0$ with $q = 5, 7$).

For each current analyzed, the amplitudes of the BBHs are manually extracted (A_{BBH}). At the same time, f_0 , f_{RSH} and f_{MEH} are obtained to calculate the slips according to (1) and (2). Using these slips, the frequency of each BBH is calculated and the amplitude at that frequency is recorded ($A_{BBH,MEH}$ and $A_{BBH,RSH}$) and compared to A_{BBH} . Figure 17 shows the error distribution (in five intervals: [0 1), [1 2), ... [10 30)), for the five BBHs considered (five figures from top to bottom) when the slip is estimated through the RSH (blue bars: $\Delta A_{RSH} = |A_{BBH} - A_{BBH,RSH}|$) and the MEH (red bars: $\Delta A_{MEH} = |A_{BBH} - A_{BBH,MEH}|$).

Overall, the accuracy achieved by both harmonics is sufficient to provide a reliable diagnosis in most of the cases. Despite this, it is clear that the quantification error committed when using the RSH is lower than with the MEH: depending on the BBH analyzed, the percentage of cases where $\Delta A < 1$ dB (first interval [0 1)), ranges from 69.6 % to 100 % for the RSH and from 56.5 % to 82.6 % for the MEH (decreasing from top to bottom). Moreover, the percentage of cases where $\Delta A > 2$ dB (intervals three, four and five summed), ranges from 0 % to 8.7 % for the RSH and from 13 % to 30.4 % for the MEH. Therefore, the probability of committing a misdiagnosis by the automatic algorithm will be higher if it uses the MEHs instead of the RSHs.

Fig. 17. Error distribution for each BBH when the slip is estimated through the RSH (blue bars) and the MEH (red bars).

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

To the authors' knowledge, [26] provides a comparative analysis between RSH- and MEH-based (referred to as REH in their work) speed estimation techniques. However, there are significant differences in scope and depth between [26] and the present work.

First, regarding accuracy, the results shown in this paper are consistent with those of [26], which also found that RSH-based estimation provides higher accuracy than MEH-based estimation (RSH errors $< 0.07\%$ vs. REH errors $< 0.3\%$ in their study). However, while [26] reached this conclusion using only three motors in the context of non-intrusive efficiency estimation, the present study confirms and generalizes this finding using 135 test-bench signals and 100 industrial measurements. Furthermore, the present paper analyzes how this accuracy difference impacts the reliability of the fault diagnosis, an aspect not addressed in [26].

Second, regarding detectability, the present work provides a comprehensive analysis that has no precedent in the literature. No prior study, including [26], has systematically compared the detectability of RSHs and MEHs in terms of existence probability (using 3643 motors), amplitude and SNR, dominance in the search band, and load dependency. These aspects are critical for an automatic SSE algorithm integrated in an MCSA system, yet they had not been addressed before. In fact, these aspects prove to be even more critical than accuracy when deciding which harmonic to use.

As for limitations, it is acknowledged that the study focuses on steady-state conditions with approximately constant supply frequency, and that the test-bench analysis is limited to a single motor type. However, these conditions are representative of the vast majority of industrial scenarios, where IMs typically operate at constant or near-constant speed within the capture windows used for diagnosis. The industrial measurements database further compensates for the test-bench limitation by covering 100 motors of very different sizes, pole pairs, power supplies, and applications.

Finally, future work will address the case of motors operating under continuously and significantly varying speed

conditions, adapting the analysis and signal processing tools to the specific characteristics of non-stationary operation. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that several of the conclusions drawn in this paper are directly extensible to transient operation, as they depend on inherent machine design characteristics rather than on the operating regime: namely, the existence probability of RSHs (governed by the R/p ratio), the influence of pole pairs on MEH amplitude and dominance, and the theoretical higher accuracy of RSH-based estimation (governed by the coefficient $60/(kR)$ in equation (5)).

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of the two main harmonics (RSHs and MEHs) used in SSE for their integration in a MCSA diagnostic system operating in the context of an Industry 4.0. The main findings and contributions are listed below:

- The statistical evidence (3643 IMs analyzed) demonstrates that most IMs (81.3% of cases) are produced with a combination R/p such that they are capable of producing RSHs of high amplitude ($k_{min} = 1, 2$). This percentage is even higher in two- and four-poles machines (93.3% of cases), which are precisely those most commonly used in industry. Therefore, from a manufacturing point of view, the probability of finding RSHs with an amplitude above the noise-floor is high. This analysis has subsequently been supported by the industrial measurement database, where the existence of RSHs of high amplitude (relative to the noise-floor level) has been observed in all motors, which have very different sizes and characteristics.
- In general terms, the SNR of RSHs is much better than that of the MEHs; according to the 100 industrial measurements database: 37.2 dB vs 18.87 dB. Moreover, the noise-floor around the RSHs tends to be lower (approximately 8 dB less), due to the greater distance to the fundamental component. This plays in favor of the RSHs detection in motors with $k_{min} > 1$ (lower amplitude) and works against the MEHs detection in those motors where they usually have lower amplitudes, such as two-poles IMs.
- Overall, RSHs present a higher % of cases of total+partial dominance than MEHs in their operating band. Moreover, dominance problems are easier to deal with RSHs due to their higher bandwidth and number of present harmonics.
- When the amplitude and dominance analysis is categorized by power rating, the observed differences between power ranges are found to be an indirect effect of the distribution of p in each range.
- There is always at least one RSH that has a direct relationship with the load level, while both MEHs have an inverse relationship. Therefore, the circumstances in which it is easier to detect a MEH (from a better SNR point of view), are precisely the least common for an industrial motor, since they normally operate between 70 and 100% of the rated load.
- Although the speed errors (compared to a 1000-line encoder) with both types of harmonics are very low, the

RSHs are able to provide much more accurate estimations in the majority of cases (up to 16 times more precise). This is in agreement with the theoretical analysis regarding the maximum speed error caused by the frequency resolution error (as seen in equation (5)). However, when using RSHs, it is desirable to reach a compromise with the length of the capture time, to keep the speed error caused by slip-frequency instabilities low.

- When analyzing the 23 cases of the industrial measurement database where the rotor asymmetry is significant (high amplitude BBHS), the MEHs provide sufficiently high accuracy for an automatic diagnostic algorithm in most cases (provided they have been precisely detected). However, there are a considerable number of cases where very small errors in the estimation of the slip lead to large errors (above 5 dB) in the quantification of the harmonic amplitude, especially, in fault harmonics with large bandwidths. On the contrary, the generally much more accurate slip estimations of the RSHs allow to keep the quantification error always below 4 dB, and below 2 dB in 91.3 % to 100% of the cases analyzed, depending on the targeted BBH.

Therefore, analyses conducted in this paper clearly show how the RSHs outperform the MEHs in each of the criteria defined to decide which type of harmonic is more reliable for a SSE algorithm. In this regard, since recent works have shown that RSHs can be used for SSE in a general and non-invasive way, it is concluded that RSH-based SSE algorithm should be the chosen one to be implemented in any automatic diagnostic system via MCSA.

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